

PRINCIPLES OF PROGRESS IN FAIRY TALES AND LITERARY FAIRY TALES.

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Fairy tale-one of the genres of folk poetic creativity, associated with the reality of life, oral stories built on the basis of philosophical-educational ideas and life problems, not devoid of artistic textures and fiction. The emergence and formation of this genre penetrates the layers of the primitive era. Ancient customs and rituals played a decisive role in this. Its development as an independent genre begins with a period when historical real phenomena are expressed in a fantastic form. Because during this period, the mythological traditions, associated with concrete things and phenomena, seed, tribe, patriarchal relations, traditional habits lost their socio-domestic function and began to acquire a strange, unusual state in the minds of people. The transformation of this historical and typological process in the fairy tale has given rise to the system of motives that make up its structure. Early examples of fairy tale motifs were didactic, while later ones acquired social meaning. Each of its motifs and episodes is described in the shell of fantastic and life fiction. The fairy tale is characterized by its own ideological-thematic direction, educational aesthetic function. Ideal dreams such as valor and heroism, justice and humanity, patriotism, true love, loyalty, fidelity are told against the background of fantastic and life fiction. High examples of morality and decency in various layers of time are glorified and oppression and violence are condemned. Consequently, fairy tales are no time idler, passtime things, they are of excellent social and historical importance all the time. The fact that fairy tales depict the reality of life on the basis of fantasy and life fiction is based on the means of magic and Magic, The Fantastic-extraordinary state of events and actions the imagination of the heroes of the past differs from other genres of folklore in their natural courage. "There are various factors in the formation of such states as spirituality, mental state, belief, that is, in your development as a perfect person, of course. One of these, the most interesting are the tales, narratives, legends that our grandparents tell. When we read them, we either listen to the famous heroes, The Brave, The Invincible Baha'is for their people, the fat guys who are ready to sacrifice the third of their nationality. We will get acquainted with the wise, wise mothers who, with their erudition, will be able to easily find

their way and get out of trouble, even in the most difficult conditions, with the wise girls who will leave even the Kings lol". Its distinctive genre features, the characters are much more widely covered in a number of works on the example of Uzbek fairy tales. Fiction is a fairytale criterion. He is a poetic tool that controls events and events, leads to a successful ending, provides dynamic action, finally determines the system of images. That is why in the plots on which fiction is based, existing events and phenomena seem far from Vitality. The spirit of fiction is felt throughout the fairy tale.

Principles of progress in fairy tales and literary fairy tales are based on several key elements that contribute to the development and evolution of the genre. These principles include:

1. Transformation: One of the central themes in fairy tales is the idea of transformation, where characters undergo a journey or change that leads to personal growth and development. This can be physical, emotional, or psychological transformation that helps the character overcome obstacles and achieve their goals.
2. Moral lessons: Fairy tales often convey moral lessons or values through the experiences of the characters. These lessons can be subtle or overt, but they serve to teach readers important life lessons about courage, kindness, perseverance, and other virtues.
3. Symbolism: Fairy tales are rich in symbolism, with characters, objects, and events often representing deeper meanings or concepts. Symbolism adds layers of complexity to the story and allows readers to interpret the tale in different ways.
4. Archetypes: Fairy tales often feature archetypal characters such as heroes, villains, mentors, and tricksters. These archetypes represent universal human qualities and experiences, making the stories relatable and timeless.
5. Narrative structure: Fairy tales typically follow a simple narrative structure with clear beginnings, middles, and endings. This structure helps to create a sense of order and resolution in the story, providing a satisfying conclusion for readers.
6. Cultural context: Fairy tales are deeply rooted in cultural traditions and beliefs, reflecting the values and norms of a particular society. Literary fairy tales may explore these cultural contexts in more depth, offering commentary on social issues or challenging traditional norms.

By understanding and applying these principles of progress in fairy tales and literary fairy tales, writers can create engaging and impactful stories that

resonate with readers across generations. Fairy tales are the stories which retell the morals and advisable conclusions that can be followed for the whole life.

The list of used literature:

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6. Jacobs J. English fairy tales and more English fairy tales. – London, 2002.– 408 p.